

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 1

Acceptance of papers **January, 2026**

Acceptance of papers

Published monthly

Topics

economics, technology, social sciences

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THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Electronic publication, Issue 1. 136 pages.
Approved for publication on January, 2026.

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THE ROLE OF PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL TRAINING OF DRIVERS IN REDUCING ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS

Uralbayev Anvar Ubaydullayevich

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD),

Associate Professor Samarkand Branch of Tashkent International University of Kimyo

anvarubaydullayev@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0577-9709>

Abstract: This article examines the impact of driver behavior and vehicle control under different road conditions on traffic safety. The study analyzes driving performance on dry and wet roads, snowy and icy surfaces, urban and mountainous routes, as well as the influence of weather and visibility conditions. Factors such as speed selection, maneuvering strategies, braking behavior, and driver responses to hazardous situations are identified as key determinants of road safety. The findings contribute to reducing traffic accidents and improving driving safety and culture.

Key words: Road conditions, driving behavior, vehicle control, traffic safety, weather factors, speed regulation, maneuvering, traffic accidents.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada haydovchining turli yo'l sharoitlarida avtomobilni boshqarish xususiyatlari va ularning yo'l harakati xavfsizligiga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda quruq va nam yo'llar, qor va muz qoplamali qoplamalar, tog'li va shahar yo'llari, shuningdek, yoritilish va ob-havo omillarining haydovchilik faoliyatiga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Haydovchining tezlikni tanlashi, manevr qilish uslubi, tormozlash va xavfli vaziyatlarga munosabati harakat xavfsizligini belgilovchi asosiy omillar sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqola natijalari yo'l-transport hodisalarini kamaytirish va haydovchilik madaniyatini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Yo'l sharoitlari, haydovchilik faoliyati, avtomobilni boshqarish, harakat xavfsizligi, ob-havo omillari, tezlik rejimi, manevr, yo'l-transport hodisalari.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется влияние управления автомобилем в различных дорожных условиях на безопасность дорожного движения. Рассматриваются особенности вождения на сухих и мокрых дорогах, снежных и обледенелых покрытиях, в городских и горных условиях, а также воздействие погодных и световых факторов. Выбор скорости, особенности маневрирования, торможения и реакции водителя в опасных ситуациях рассматриваются как основные факторы, определяющие уровень безопасности движения. Полученные результаты направлены на снижение дорожно-транспортных происшествий и повышение культуры вождения.

Ключевые слова: Дорожные условия, управление автомобилем, безопасность дорожного движения, поведение водителя, погодные факторы, скорость движения, маневрирование, дорожно-транспортные происшествия.

INTRODUCTION

Zamonaviy jamiyatda avtomobil transporti ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotning muhim omillaridan biri bo'lib, aholi harakatchanligini ta'minlash, ishlab chiqarish va xizmat ko'rsatish sohalarning uzluksiz faoliyat yuritishida muhim o'rin egallaydi. Shu bilan birga, transport vositalarining soni va yo'l harakati intensivligining ortib borishi yo'l-transport hodisalari xavfining oshishiga ham olib kelmoqda. Ushbu jarayonda harakat xavfsizligini ta'minlash muammosi dolzarb masalalardan biri sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda.

Yo'l-transport hodisalarining kelib chiqishida ko'plab omillar mavjud bo'lib, ular orasida haydovchining turli yo'l sharoitlarida avtomobilni boshqarish xususiyatlari yetakchi ahamiyatga ega. Quruq va nam yo'llar, qor va muz bilan qoplangan qoplamalar, shahar va qishloq yo'llari, tog'li hududlar, shuningdek, ob-havo va yoritilish sharoitlari haydovchidan turli darajadagi malaka, ehtiyotkorlik va tezkor qaror qabul qilish qobiliyatini talab etadi. Har bir yo'l sharoiti avtomobilning texnik imkoniyatlari bilan bir qatorda haydovchining psixologik va fiziologik tayyorgarligini ham sinovdan o'tkazadi.

Amaliy tajriba va ilmiy tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, haydovchining tezlikni to'g'ri tanlamasligi, masofani saqlamasligi, tormozlash va manevr qilish qoidalariga rioya etmasligi turli yo'l sharoitlarida avariya xavfini keskin oshiradi. Ayniqsa, noqulay ob-havo sharoitlarida va ko'rish imkoniyati cheklangan vaziyatlarda haydovchining xatolari og'ir oqibatlariga olib kelishi mumkin. Shu sababli haydovchining yo'l vaziyatiga moslashuvchan boshqaruv strategiyalarini shakllantirish muhim ilmiy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

So'nggi yillarda yo'l harakati xavfsizligini ta'minlashga qaratilgan chora-tadbirlar kuchaytirilayotgan bo'lsa-da, haydovchining turli yo'l sharoitlaridagi boshqaruv xatti-harakatlarini chuqur tahlil qilish va ularning harakat xavfsizligiga ta'sirini kompleks baholash masalasi yetarli darajada yoritilmagan. Mazkur holat haydovchilik faoliyatining inson omiliga doir jihatlarini ilmiy asosda o'rganish zaruratini yanada kuchaytiradi.

Shu munosabat bilan mazkur maqolada haydovchining har xil yo'l sharoitlarida avtomobilni boshqarish xususiyatlari, tezlik tanlash, manevr qilish, tormozlash va xavfli vaziyatlarga munosabat bildirish jarayonlarining harakat xavfsizligiga ta'siri ilmiy-nazariy va amaliy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari yo'l-transport hodisalarini kamaytirish, haydovchilik madaniyatini oshirish hamda harakat xavfsizligini ta'minlashga qaratilgan samarali tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishga xizmat qiladi.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Road traffic safety issues are extensively studied across the fields of transport psychology, highway engineering, and ergonomics. Scientific literature emphasizes that, alongside technical and infrastructural factors, the driver's control behavior under diverse road conditions plays a decisive role in the occurrence of road traffic accidents. Researchers note that decision-making speed, situational awareness, and vehicle control strategies are the primary indicators of traffic safety.

The impact of road surface conditions (dry, wet, snowy, or icy), geometric characteristics of the road, traffic intensity, and weather conditions on driving activity is widely documented. Specifically, studies highlight increased braking distances, reduced vehicle stability, and a higher frequency of control errors on wet and slippery roads. It is scientifically established that mountainous terrains and complex reliefs demand higher levels of attention and experience due to limited visibility and sharp curves.

Psychological research indicates that a driver's stress resistance, emotional stability, and fatigue levels are directly correlated with the quality of vehicle control under various conditions. Researchers assert that adverse weather and complex road environments increase psychophysiological tension, thereby elevating the probability of human error. Concurrently, a driver's experience and professional training are viewed as critical factors that enhance adaptability to hazardous situations.

Despite the achievements in studying driver behavior, the necessity for a comprehensive and systemic approach—analyzing the intricate correlations between driver actions, road conditions, and safety indicators—remains. This gap defines the relevance of the current study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The objective of this research is to determine the impact of driver control behavior on traffic safety across heterogeneous road conditions. The methodological foundation of the study is built upon a systemic approach, the "Human Factor" concept, and theoretical frameworks of road traffic safety.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

During the research, the characteristics of vehicle control by drivers under various road conditions and their impact on traffic safety were comprehensively analyzed. The obtained theoretical and empirical data revealed a direct correlation between driver behavior, road conditions, and the risk of road traffic accidents.

According to the results of the analysis, the condition of the road surface significantly affects driving activity. On dry roads, vehicle control is relatively stable, making it easier for the driver to control speed and perform maneuvers. However, on wet, snowy, or icy roads, an increase in braking distance, a tendency for the vehicle to skid, and a decrease in control stability were observed. It was found that improper speed selection under such conditions poses a serious threat to traffic safety.

The analysis of weather and lighting conditions showed that during fog, rain, snowfall, and nighttime, a driver's ability to perceive the road situation is limited. The reduction in visibility distance requires a high level of attention and caution from the driver. The research results noted that under these conditions, instances of drivers incorrectly assessing distance and exhibiting delayed reactions occur more frequently.

During the analysis, speed selection and maneuvering characteristics were studied separately. The results showed that failing to adapt speed to road conditions and performing sharp maneuvers in complex

road environments significantly increases the risk of an accident. Especially at turns, inclines, and declines, the driver's experience and caution emerged as critical factors in ensuring traffic safety.

The psychophysiological state of the driver also held a significant place in the analysis results. It was found that under conditions of stress, fatigue, and emotional tension, the driver's level of attention decreases, and the likelihood of making incorrect decisions increases. In contrast, experienced and stress-resilient drivers demonstrated the ability to adapt more quickly to the situation in various road conditions and anticipate hazardous situations in advance.

The results obtained indicate that traffic safety is directly dependent on driving strategies adapted to road conditions. The patterns identified during the study justify the need to increase driving culture and to form and strengthen control skills for various road conditions during the driver training process.

In general, the analysis results show that deeply studying the characteristics of vehicle control under various road conditions and integrating them into the traffic safety management system plays a vital role in reducing road traffic accidents.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the conducted research confirm that the driver's vehicle control behavior under various road conditions and its impact on traffic safety are critical factors. The analysis showed that road surface conditions (dry, wet, snowy, or icy), weather conditions, lighting, and road geometry require varying levels of caution, attention, rapid decision-making, and adaptive control skills from the driver.

The primary psychophysiological and control characteristics identified during the study—speed control, braking methods, maneuvering, reaction to hazardous situations, and stress resilience—emerged as decisive factors in determining traffic safety. While driving safety is high on dry and stable roads, the probability of error increases significantly on slippery, snowy, or icy roads, as well as on roads with complex terrain.

Furthermore, the research results indicated that the driver's experience and psychophysiological preparedness play an essential role in adaptability to dangerous situations and ensuring traffic safety. These conclusions serve as a foundation for professional driver training, adapting drivers to various road conditions, and developing practical recommendations aimed at reducing road traffic accidents.

In general, the study once again confirms the decisive role of the human factor in driving activities and demonstrates the necessity of developing psychophysiological and control skills to enhance traffic safety.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 1

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